

E3.3.1 Initial design for data management and adaptive learning in 6G v2.0

Publication date: 30/04/2024

[6GENABLERS-AI]
[6GENABLERS]

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
I+D**

Financiado por la Unión Europea
NextGenerationEU

GOBIERNO
DE ESPAÑA

Plan de Recuperación,
Transformación
y Resiliencia

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	6GENABLERS-SP1-L1-P3
Líder del PT	OPTARE
Editor Principal	Guillermo Candela Belmonte
Contribuyentes	
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación	
PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo	
PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

versión	Histórico de versiones del documento			
	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
v1.0	Guillermo C.	Inicial	26/04/2024	Versión inicial
v2.0	Guillermo C.	Revisión	30/04/2024	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Move references at the end of document. 2. Update figures 4,5 and 9. 3. Update page 12

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
List of Tables	3
List of Figures	4
List of Acronyms	4
1. Executive Summary	5
2. Introduction	5
3. Objectives	5
3.1. Efficient Data Management at the Network Edge	5
3.2. Adaptive Learning Mechanisms and Data Management.....	6
4. Integration Monitoring System with OpenNebula	6
4.1 Review and Extension of OpenNebula Probes	7
4.2 Implementation of OpenTelemetry and OpenCollector	8
4.3 Integration with Existing Monitoring Systems.....	9
4.3.1 OpenTelemetry Collector and Instrumentation CRD	10
5 Integration Feature Store with OpenNebula AIOps	12
5.1 Observability backend	13
5.2 ETL Integration.....	14
5.3 Feature Store Integration.....	14
5.3.1 Key concepts in Feast.....	15
5.3.2 Feast infrastructure	16
5.3.3 Validating Data with Feast and Great Expectations.....	17
5.3.4 Feast API	17
6 Conclusions	19
References	19

List of Tables

Table 1 Acronyms.....	4
Table 2 vBS features.....	13

List of Figures

Figure 1 OpenNebula Monitoring system process.....	7
Figure 2 Integration with Existing Monitoring System.....	10
Figure 3 OpenTelemetry configuration structure.....	10
Figure 4 Integration Feature Store with OpenNebula AIOps.....	12
Figure 5 Adaptive Learning Mechanisms and Data Management.....	13
Figure 6 ETL integration.....	14
Figure 7 Feast components.....	15
Figure 8 Feast structure.....	15
Figure 9 Feast infrastructure and integration with OpenNebula.....	16
Figure 10 Skew detection and drift detection.....	17

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ZSM	Zero-touch network and Service Management
VM	Virtual Machine
6G	Sixth generation of wireless communications technologies
CPU	Unidad Central de Procesamiento
API	Application Programming Interfaces
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
NeSy	Neuro-Symbolic
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations

Table 1 Acronyms

1. Executive Summary

Deliverable E.3.3.1 present the culmination of efforts outlined in tasks A3.2/A3.3 of the 6GENABLERS project (IA para 6G: Ultra Automatización y Optimización, reference number TSI-063000-2021-10). The proposed architecture in this document efficiently handles large volumes of heterogeneous data generated at the network edge and integrates methods to facilitate adaptive learning, which will dynamically respond to changing network conditions. Additionally, this design will be included on a closed automation system that optimizes resource utilization without manual intervention, in line with ETSI ZSM standards for self-optimization, self-configuration, and self-healing, demonstrating dynamic scaling and optimization capabilities of edge-based applications using telemetry data and AI models.

2. Introduction

The transition to 6G networks is a significant advance in terms of capacity, speed, and complexity, requiring critical innovations in data management and machine learning. This initial design is aligned with the objectives of the 6GENABLERS project, focused especially on tasks SP1-L1-P3-A3.2 and SP1-L1-P3-A3.3, addressing these challenges through an architecture that not only manages the large scale and heterogeneity of network data, but also adapts learning methods to maximize network performance and efficiency in real time. This document highlights the integration of a proactive monitoring system and the implementation of a telemetry platform by OPTARE, which improves the response capacity and autonomous management of the network.

3. Objectives

3.1. Efficient Data Management at the Network Edge

The objective is to develop efficient mechanisms for the distribution, management, and visibility of massive and heterogeneous data at the network edge, including lifecycle management of data. This aims to significantly reduce communication overhead through effective sharing of data and trained models among federated nodes, thereby facilitating transfer learning. To enhance these capabilities, we will implement methods that provide advanced data visibility techniques. This ensures that critical information is readily accessible when needed for decision-making processes. According [Ref1] the integration of **OpenNebula's** Monitoring system with Open telemetry platform provided by **OPTARE** plays a crucial role in this setup.

This integration not only benefits from advanced monitoring and telemetry but also enhances the default virtual machine monitoring by including a wider range of metrics. Consequently, this enables more effective and data-driven optimization of the network, significantly improving real-time resource management and network performance.

3.2. Adaptive Learning Mechanisms and Data Management

The objective of this initiative is to apply and validate adaptive learning methods that dynamically adjust to the changing conditions of the network. This involves using advanced learning techniques such as incremental learning, transfer learning, knowledge distillation, and reinforcement learning. These methods are crucial for effectively managing the large scale and heterogeneity of network data, ensuring that the learning processes are continuously updated and adjusted to optimize network performance and efficiency in real time.

To support these objectives, **OPTARE** integrates **FEAST** (Feature Store) to facilitate efficient management of data features, crucial for both offline training and online inference. This integration ensures consistency in model behaviour across different operational stages and enhances data visibility and access during critical decision-making processes.

OPTARE contributes its advanced telemetry platform that facilitates the collection and real-time access to critical data, seamlessly integrating with FEAST, which acts as a centralized repository for efficient feature management. **OpenNebula** uses these data and features in its decision engine to perform automated scaling and resource optimization without manual intervention, while according [Ref2] **i2CAT** focuses on analysis/NeSy predictive model and MLOps pipelines along with OpenNebula's intelligent orchestrator form a zero-touch closed control loop.

4. Integration Monitoring System with OpenNebula

According [Ref1] OpenNebula monitoring system is recognized as a vital component for ensuring the health and efficiency of both hosts and VMs. It provides essential information about their operational status, playing a crucial role in maintaining system integrity.

OpenNebula Monitoring Subsystem Overview:

The monitoring¹ framework is spearheaded by the onemonitord daemon, an integral part of the OpenNebula Daemon (oned). This service is designed for the continuous collection of critical data points concerning hosts and VMs, including resource utilization, performance metrics, and health indicators.

Data Collection Methodology:

Data is gathered through a series of probes—scripts developed by OpenNebula, running internally within the hosts (refer to Figure 1 for the OpenNebula Monitoring system process).

¹https://docs.opennebula.io/6.8/installation_and_configuration/opennebula_services/monitoring.html

Figure 1 OpenNebula Monitoring system process.

To optimize the integration plan for OpenNebula with OpenTelemetry and OpenCollector, incorporating advanced techniques and operational efficiency strategies based on the latest monitoring practices and technologies is crucial. Here is an improved version of the integration plan that includes key elements. Enhanced Integration Plan for OpenNebula with OpenTelemetry and OpenCollector.

4.1 Review and Extension of OpenNebula Probes

Probe Updates: Develop or enhance existing probes within OpenNebula to capture more detailed metrics suited to dynamic 6G environments, including auto-instrumentation to minimize manual intervention and configuration errors.

- Advanced Metric Collection:** Using the strength of the existing monitoring subsystem, which operates through a dedicated daemon (onemonitord) and a set of probes, the probe software can be improved to gather more detailed data. This must include advanced performance indicators such as real-time vBS performance, detailed memory usage patterns, and CPU load per process (see section 5.1 table 2), which are crucial for optimizing operations in 6G environments.
- Auto-Instrumentation Capabilities:** Updated probes will incorporate auto-instrumentation technology², supported by OpenTelemetry for various programming languages such as .NET, Java, Node.js, Python, and Go. This feature allows probes to automatically detect and monitor new instances of virtual machines or changes in the host's state, dynamically adjusting their monitoring parameters without human intervention.

² <https://opentelemetry.io/docs/languages/>

Integration with OpenTelemetry: Ensure that updated probes integrate effectively with OpenTelemetry using specific adapters that transform and enrich the collected data with relevant metadata, facilitating analysis and correlation.

- **Effective Data Integration:** The enhanced probes need to integrate seamlessly with OpenTelemetry. This involves using specific adapters that can transform the raw data collected into a format enriched with relevant metadata. This metadata could include detailed context about the operational state of the host or VM, significantly improving the usefulness of the data for deeper analysis and better correlation.
- **Metadata Enrichment:** Leveraging the capabilities of OpenTelemetry, metadata such as Kubernetes tags or custom tags that describe the workload or service level can be added to the monitoring data. This provides critical insights that enable network operators to trace issues back to specific virtual machines or host environments.
- **Leveraging Existing Infrastructure:** The current architecture of OpenNebula's monitoring system, which involves pushing data from the hosts to the frontend via a lightweight protocol, is well-suited for integration with OpenTelemetry. OpenTelemetry can be configured to accept this data directly from onemondord or through an intermediary that preprocesses the data, enhancing scalability in data handling and reducing latency in data processing.

This integration strategy enhances OpenNebula's ability to manage and monitor complex network environments effectively, ensuring readiness for future technological advancements and operational demands.

4.2 Implementation of OpenTelemetry and OpenCollector

OpenTelemetry Configuration: Deploy and configure the OpenTelemetry agent on nodes and VMs to enhance monitoring capabilities. This setup should leverage data enrichment with Kubernetes metadata and advanced metrics collection through specialized receivers.

Integration of Specialized Receivers³:

- **Kubeletstats Receiver:** This receiver is essential for pulling detailed metrics related to nodes, pods, and containers directly from the API server on a kubelet. It provides critical insights into resource utilization and system performance.
- **Host Metrics Receiver:** Implement this receiver to collect essential host metrics directly from Kubernetes nodes. It gathers comprehensive system-level operation data, crucial for deep performance analysis.
- **Data Enrichment:** Use the Kubernetes Attributes Processor to enrich incoming telemetry from applications with Kubernetes-specific metadata. This enrichment allows for more contextual monitoring and troubleshooting, enhancing operational visibility across the infrastructure.

³ <https://opentelemetry.io/docs/kubernetes/collector/components/>

Utilizing OpenCollector:

Implement OpenCollector as a powerful intermediary that processes, transforms, and efficiently routes the collected metrics to various destinations. This setup ensures that data are handled optimally, preventing duplication, and promoting efficient data flow.

Advanced Data Routing and Transformation:

- **Filelog Receiver:** Collect and manage logs from Kubernetes as well as application logs written to stdout/stderr. This receiver is vital for a comprehensive log management strategy, ensuring all operational logs are captured and analyzed.
- **Kubernetes Cluster Receiver:** Integrate this receiver to collect overarching cluster-level metrics and entity events, providing a macroscopic view of the cluster's health and activity.
- **Kubernetes Objects Receiver:** This receiver collects Kubernetes objects such as events directly from the Kubernetes API server. It is instrumental in tracking state changes and system events that could influence operational decisions.
- **Prometheus Receiver:** Incorporate this receiver to handle metrics in Prometheus format, seamlessly integrating with existing Prometheus-based monitoring setups.

Comprehensive Data Processing: OpenCollector not only captures and consolidates data from these diverse sources but also enhances the data through transformation processes before routing it to systems like Prometheus, Jaeger, and OpenSearch. This ensures that the data exported is of high quality, rich in context, and ready for detailed analysis and visualization.

This refined strategy enhances OpenNebula's ability to manage and monitor complex network environments effectively. By integrating advanced OpenTelemetry components tailored for Kubernetes monitoring, the system becomes more robust, adaptable, and capable of meeting the demands of advanced network management tasks with minimal human intervention. This setup is particularly beneficial in dynamic and complex infrastructures such as those encountered in 6G environments, where precision and real-time data processing are crucial.

4.3 Integration with Existing Monitoring Systems

Compatibility with Prometheus: OpenTelemetry is configured to export data to Prometheus, maintaining the existing visualization and alert capabilities of the system. This not only preserves the already used functions but also enhances integration with alerts based on enriched and contextualized metrics, allowing for more precise and context-aware monitoring of operations.

Data Export Flexibility: OpenCollector is adjusted to allow data export to other analysis and monitoring systems, such as Jaeger and OpenSearch. This enhances the system's interoperability and adaptability to different network environments, allowing for more flexible configuration and responding to various operational needs.

E3.3.1 Initial design for data management and adaptive learning in 6G

Figure 2 Integration with Existing Monitoring System

Figure 2 illustrates the integration of new components with OpenNebula, enhancing its monitoring capabilities:

4.3.1 OpenTelemetry Collector and Instrumentation CRD

Integrated within the Kubernetes infrastructure and host metrics, this OpenTelemetry components utilizes the kubeletstats and host receivers to collect metrics directly, as well as metrics auto generated by CRD Instrumentation. It offers a comprehensive and refined view of the infrastructure's performance and health, which is vital for proactive management and timely problem resolution.

Configuration structure

Figure 3 OpenTelemetry configuration structure.

Receivers collect telemetry from one or more sources. They can be pull or push based and may support one or more data sources.

Many receivers come with default settings, so that specifying the name of the receiver is enough to configure it.

Data sources:

- **Kubeletstats Receiver:** pulls node, pod, and container metrics from the API server on a kubelet.
- **Kubernetes Cluster Receiver:** collects cluster-level metrics and entity events.
- **Kubernetes Objects Receiver:** collects objects, such as events, from the Kubernetes API server.
- **Host Metrics Receiver:** scrapes host metrics from Kubernetes nodes.

Processors take the data collected by receivers and modify or transform it before sending it to the exporters. Data processing happens according to rules or settings defined for each processor, which might include filtering, dropping, renaming, or recalculating telemetry, among other operations. The order of the processors in a pipeline determines the order of the processing operations that the Collector applies to the signal.

Processors are optional, although some are recommended:

By default, no processors are enabled. Depending on the data source, it may be recommended that multiple processors be enabled. Processors must be enabled for every data source and not all processors support all data sources. In addition, it is important to note that the order of processors matters. The order in each section below is the best practice.

1. `memory_limiter`
2. Any sampling or initial filtering processors
3. Any processor relying on sending source from Context (e.g. `k8sattributes`)
4. `batch`
5. Any other processors

The refined data are **exported** to various observability platforms such as InfluxDB2, Jaeger, and OpenSearch. These platforms enable the analysis and visualization of data, providing network operators with tools for effective monitoring and informed decision-making.

This combination of configurations and components reflects a robust and adaptable system, capable of handling complex monitoring and analysis demands in dynamic environments, leveraging advanced capabilities of OpenTelemetry and the innovations brought by Optare.

5 Integration Feature Store with OpenNebula AIOps

According [Ref1] one of the main functionalities of OpenNebula AIOps is to turn metrics associated with OneFlow Services (application-specific such as number of requests per second, VM resource usage such as CPU, and user-defined) collected by the monitoring system into actionable insights, i.e. determining the right amount of virtual machines of each Service role that are needed in a certain time to keep the application performance and the service quality at predefined levels.

OPTARE offers an advanced telemetry platform that enhances data acquisition and ensures instantaneous access to critical information. This platform is seamlessly integrated (see figure 4) with the Feature Store (FEAST), which functions as a centralized repository for streamlined feature management. Through this integration, i2CAT leverages both online and offline feature services in its inference and training workflows, facilitating autonomous scaling and resource optimization by OpenNebula, thus eliminating the need for manual oversight.

OPTARE's telemetry platform exposes data in both offline (training) and online (inference) modes. A transparent namespace in the MLOps pipeline utilizes this telemetry data to train and refine the proactive CPU prediction model NeSy. The predictions are then served to OpenNebula's decision engine, co-located with the orchestrator, to perform scaling actions.

This closed-loop automation process ensures that the architecture can adapt to changing conditions and optimize resource utilization without manual intervention. ETSI ZSM emphasizes closed-loop automation to achieve self-optimization, self-configuration, and self-healing capabilities, which this architecture demonstrates by dynamically scaling and optimizing Edge applications based on telemetry data and AI models.

Figure 4 Integration Feature Store with OpenNebula AIOps

Figure 5 details the OPTARE platform, highlighting its main components:

- Observability Backend
- ETL
- Feature Store

Figure 5 Adaptive Learning Mechanisms and Data Management

5.1 Observability backend

In Section 4.1 was described the importance of updating and enhancing the **OpenNebula** agents and probes for the effective collection of metrics is highlighted. This upgrade is crucial for properly integrating these agents with the Opentelemetry telemetry system provided by **OPTARE**, with the aim of significantly expanding monitoring capabilities. Efficient integration between OpenNebula and OPTARE will enhance advanced telemetry, playing a fundamental role in accessing a broader range of metrics meticulously stored in a time-series database. Enhanced access to metrics from **vBS** is essential, as it facilitates deeper understanding and more effective management of network resources through more detailed analysis.

According to [Ref2], **i2CAT** implement the training of the NeSy predictive model using data from the vBSs. These vBSs are configured within specific sets of CPU cores, each allocated distinct time-sharing resources, and are associated with a context that includes traffic demands and detailed statistics on the Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) for both Uplink (UL) and Downlink (DL).

Within the OPTARE-OpenNebula integration, the metrics derived from vBSs will be instrumental in developing the following features:

Feature	Description
mcs_dl_i	Downlink MCS index of vBS i
mcs_ul_i	Uplink MCS index of vBS i
dl_kbps_i	Downlink traffic demand in kbps of vBS i
ul_kbps_i	Uplink traffic demand in kbps of vBS i
cpu_set	Computing set used by vBS i

Table 2 vBS features

5.2 ETL Integration

This section details the mechanism for synchronize observability backend (time-series data base) with the offline database (warehouse), which serves as the data source for our feature store platform. This process will be executed through the Apache Airflow workflow orchestration, establishing connections to the time-series and PostgreSQL databases.

Figure 6 ETL integration.

The ETL processes will be defined through Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAG) created to specify the tasks of data extraction, optional transformation, and loading, as well as their execution frequency. The extraction task collects the necessary data from observability backend, and the transformation processes these data as needed before the loading task inserts them into offline store (PostgreSQL). Once active, the DAG runs automatically as scheduled, using the Airflow interface to monitor progress and resolve issues. Finally, continuous adjustments and improvements are made to the process, based on observed performance and business needs, to maintain the efficiency and effectiveness of the system.

5.3 Feature Store Integration

Feast is an open-source framework⁴ for storing and serving features to machine learning models. It aims to facilitate the retrieval of feature data from different sources and to this end provides a unified environment for feature management.

⁴ <https://docs.feast.dev/>

E3.3.1 Initial design for data management and adaptive learning in 6G

Figure 7 Feast components.

With Feast, machine learning and data science teams can:

- Store their features in offline or online repositories (more on the differences between offline and online repositories later).
- Combine features from different sources for training, analysis, and feature engineering.
- Retrieve fresh feature data for inference.
- Reuse features across different projects and models.

5.3.1 Key concepts in Feast

Feast implements hierarchical feature storage to help you store and manage features. Feast feature repository has the following structure:

Figure 8 Feast structure.

Project: A project is a collection of related features and their data sources. Projects are isolated from each other, and you can't reuse features from one project in another.

Feature view: A feature view is a group of feature data from a specific data source. Feature views allow you to consistently define features and their data sources, enabling the reuse of feature groups across a project. If your features are stored in more than one location, you can specify a feature view for each location and later join all the features together. Feature views make the addition of new features to your existing data very easy as well — as you gather new groups of features, you can create separate feature views for them and then merge them with your old data.

Data source: In Feast, each feature view has a data source. A data source is where the raw feature data is stored (PostgreSQL). You can have as many data sources as you want, but you can't mix different types of sources together.

Feature service: A feature service is an object that contains features from one or more feature views. You can use feature services to create logically related groups of feature views.

Entity: In practical terms, entities can be the individuals or objects that your feature data relates to. Feast also uses entities to correctly join data from different feature views.

Timestamps: Feast uses timestamps to ensure that features from different sources are joined in the correct chronological order. Primarily, this is so that you can avoid using very old data for training or prediction.

Dataset: A dataset is a group of feature views and entities. Feast datasets allow engineers to combine data from different feature views for analysis and training.

5.3.2 Feast infrastructure

Figure 9 Feast infrastructure and integration with OpenNebula.

Figure 9 displays the architecture of a Feast project. Below are described diagram components:

Offline store: The offline store (PostgreSQL) is where you store your features. In the terminology of Feast, the offline store contains historical features that you can use for analysis or training. Feast can both retrieve and write data to the offline store. This type of store is “offline” because it is located outside a Feast environment.

Online store: The online store (Redis) is where Feast stores features for low-latency access. The online store is designed to accelerate inference.

Feature repo: A feature repository contains the definitions of a Feast feature store. It defines where features are stored, how they should be retrieved, and what they contain.

Registry: A registry is a catalog of feature definitions and their metadata. It defines the infrastructure of your feature repository and where feature data comes from.

5.3.3 Validating Data with Feast and Great Expectations

Feast supported only data profiling and validation, though its roadmap included things like training-serving skew detection and drift detection.

Figure 10 Skew detection and drift detection.

To support these functions, Feast relies on the third-party Python package Great Expectations. Great Expectations is a popular framework for data validation and profiling, and it can help you make sure that your data's statistical makeup matches your assumptions and expectations.

Great Expectations has a very wide range of functions that we won't be exploring in this tutorial. Instead, we will cover the basics so that you understand how you can use Feast with Great Expectations. Then, you can check out Great Expectations on your own to start doing more advanced validation checks.

5.3.4 Feast API

To enhance the integration of OpenNebula with Feast, we propose the development of an API that encapsulates Feast functionality within a user-friendly interface. This approach aims to simplify the user experience by providing intuitive access to Feast's capabilities through a streamlined and easy-to-navigate UI. This integration will enable users to leverage the full potential of Feast's feature store capabilities more efficiently, facilitating smoother operations and improved usability.

API endpoints definition:· **/clone_repo**

Handles the cloning of feature store repositories from GitHub.

· **/get_store**

Loads the feature store from the cloned directory.

· **/get_feature_views**

Allows us to retrieve the feature views registered in our feature store.

· **/get_feature_names**

Allows us to get the feature names for a specific feature view.

· **/get_entities**

Allows us to get the entities registered in the feature store. More specifically, the endpoint returns the names of the entities and their descriptions.

· **/register_entity_df**

Create and save entity DataFrames.

· **/save_dataset**

Created entity DataFrame to save one or more feature views to a dataset.

· **/materialize**

Standard materialization

· **/materialize_incremental**

Incremental materialization.

/get_historical_features

Get historical features to training models.

/get_online_features

Get online features to inference predictions.

6 Conclusions

The document presents an integration of OpenNebula's monitoring system with the Open Telemetry platform within the 6GENABLERS project, highlighting how this synergy effectively manages large volumes of heterogeneous data and applies adaptive learning techniques to respond dynamically to network changes without manual intervention. This integration enhances data management and network performance through advanced telemetry and monitoring systems, facilitated by OPTARE, and the incorporation of FEAST for efficient data feature management. Additionally, it discusses plans to enhance monitoring capabilities and the strategic implementation of OpenTelemetry and OpenCollector, which include improving data collection and integrating with existing systems such as Prometheus to further optimize observability and operability in complex network environments.

References

- [Ref1] 6GENABLERS-SP1-L2-P2-E4.3.1 Initial Design of Smart Resource Interconnection for Efficient and Intelligent Orchestration Processes, v0.1, 04/04/2024.
- [Ref2] 6GENABLERS-SP1-L2-P2-E4.3.2 Initial design of zero-touch and proactive network management, v1.0, 31/03/2024.